

What Can Neuroscience Now Measure and Test?

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Overview video of two-minutes: <https://share.descript.com/embed/pd7t6XNtXQF>

Neuroscience has changed in practical ways over the past decade. A persistent claim in some educational and popular science writing is that neuroscience, particularly at the cellular level, remains largely speculative - that the field "knows little" about how the brain actually works. That framing deserves scrutiny. In many areas, we can now measure brain activity directly rather than infer it from behaviour alone, and we can often test explanations by manipulating neural activity and checking whether performance changes predictably. This article outlines the key measurement, imaging, and modelling capabilities that now exist, with enough context to help readers new to these techniques understand what each does and why it matters. Much of the finest cellular detail comes from animal models; in humans, comparable access is usually limited to clinical contexts (such as epilepsy monitoring) and to non-invasive imaging.

What We Can Now Measure at the Cellular and Circuit Level

At the cellular level, researchers can directly observe and quantify neural activity, the electrical and chemical signalling of individual brain cells, in living, behaving animals. A major advance has been the development of high-density silicon probes called Neuropixels. These are tiny electrode arrays, thinner than a human hair, that can be inserted into brain tissue to detect the electrical "spikes" fired by individual neurons (nerve cells). The original Neuropixels probe enabled simultaneous recordings from hundreds of individual neurons with single-cell resolution across multiple brain regions (Jun et al., 2017). A second-generation version, Neuropixels 2.0, extended this capability to thousands of neurons tracked over weeks and months in freely moving animals (Steinmetz et al., 2021). Optical methods also provide powerful access to neural signalling. Techniques such as ultrafast imaging and genetically encoded indicators, molecules engineered to glow when a neuron becomes active, enable researchers to visualise neural signalling in targeted cell types and scale from single neurons to large populations in awake preparations (Nguyen et al., 2025).

At the anatomical level, a technique called electron microscopy-based connectomics now reconstructs the physical wiring between neurons at nanometre resolution, fine enough to see individual synapses (the junctions where one neuron communicates with another). Named *Nature Methods* Method of the Year for 2025, this approach maps synaptic connections across substantial tissue volumes, grounding claims about "circuits" in measured structure rather than in mostly conceptual diagrams (Nature Methods, 2025).

What We Can Measure at the Systems Level

At the systems level, methods such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and electroencephalography (EEG) measure activity across distributed brain networks during attention, memory, decision-making, language, and other functions. These tools differ in what they do best:

- **EEG** measures electrical activity at the scalp. It is fast, but spatial precision is limited.
- **MEG** measures magnetic fields produced by neural activity. It is also fast and can localise activity somewhat better than EEG in some contexts, but it is expensive and sensitive to setup.

- **fMRI** measures a blood-oxygen signal (an indirect marker of neural activity). It has good spatial coverage but slower temporal resolution, and it is not a direct readout of neuronal firing.

A major recent shift is the push to integrate these tools so that timing and location information complement each other. Multimodal approaches, combining signals from multiple imaging methods, are increasingly used in leading cognitive and clinical research programs, especially when the question requires both temporal detail (milliseconds) and network-level localisation (centimetres) (Baghdadi et al., 2025).

Bridging Micro and Macro Levels

A key question for educational neuroscience is whether cellular-level mechanisms are relevant to the kinds of learning, training, and behaviour change educators care about. The most defensible answer is: sometimes, but not always, and the bridge must be built carefully.

One helpful example is dendritic processing. Dendrites, the branching extensions of a neuron that receive incoming signals, matter for linking scales because dendritic arbours (the full tree of branches) can receive inputs from multiple, widely separated brain regions. This means that a single neuron can sample and integrate signals from distributed networks. In hippocampal area CA1, a region central to memory formation, distinct dendritic compartments receive inputs from neighbouring areas CA2 and CA3 and from the entorhinal cortex. These compartments support local computations and a form of synaptic strengthening called plasticity, processes that can now be imaged and linked to learning and navigation in behaving animals (Moore et al., 2025; Nguyen et al., 2025). Multiscale modelling increasingly uses micro-scale properties, such as neurotransmitter systems, receptor distributions, and dendritic integration rules, to explain macro-scale fMRI patterns and network dynamics observed in whole-brain imaging (Krejcar & Namazi, 2025; Lawn et al., 2023). The point is not that we can "read thoughts", but that we can increasingly connect specific biological mechanisms to specific, testable predictions about network dynamics. In practical terms, it is now feasible to trace information flow from identified inputs onto particular dendritic branches, through local dendritic spikes, to the neuron's main output signal, and from there into the large-scale functional networks that psychology and education typically study.

Integrated Programs Linking Structure and Function

These techniques are no longer used in isolation. Rather than using separate studies for structure and function, some programs now link physiology and wiring within the same tissue. A landmark example is the functional connectomics work from the MICrONS Consortium (2025), which combines large-scale physiological recordings with dense, synapse-level anatomical reconstructions across multiple areas of the mouse visual cortex. This kind of functional connectomics, mapping both what neurons do and how they are wired, represents a qualitative shift from studying activity or anatomy alone. In parallel, whole-brain cell-type atlases now provide detailed, empirically derived taxonomies and spatial maps of neuronal cell types in the adult mouse brain, improving the biological precision of claims about circuitry and function (Yao et al., 2023).

What It Means to "Test" in Neuroscience

In everyday language, "test" can mean "measure". In neuroscience, testing usually implies something stronger: causal evidence. That often involves perturbation methods, experimentally increasing or decreasing activity in specific neurons or pathways, followed by checks to see whether outcomes change in a predicted direction. In animals, this includes techniques such as optogenetics (using light to control genetically modified neurons) and chemogenetics (using

designer drugs to activate engineered receptors in specific cell types). These methods can increase or decrease activity in defined cell types or pathways with remarkable precision. In humans, causal testing is more limited but still present, especially in clinical settings and through non-invasive stimulation methods such as transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS). The key idea for students is this: measurement tells us what the brain is doing; causal testing helps us decide whether a brain process is actually contributing to an outcome.

Modelling Has Matured, but Claims Still Need Discipline

The modelling landscape has also moved beyond the "we know little" default posture. Modern analysis methods can extract meaningful structure from large-scale recordings, including population-level patterns invisible at the single-neuron level (Cunningham & Yu, 2014; Stringer & Pachitariu, 2024). Data-driven models can now predict how neurons will respond to stimuli they have never encountered before and generalise to new stimulus conditions, reflecting progress towards predictive digital twin-type models, computational replicas of neural circuits that are explicitly evaluated against empirical recordings (Wang et al., 2025). High-performance computing efforts have built large-scale biophysical simulations at the cortical scale, constrained by measured cellular and synaptic properties and testable against observed dynamics. A recent project on the Fugaku supercomputer, for example, simulated the entire mouse cortex at a microscopic level, comprising 9 million biophysical neurons and 26 billion synapses (Kuriyama et al., 2025). Multiscale brain models explicitly aim to bridge microscopic and macroscopic levels by using cellular and molecular parameters to reproduce network-level dynamics measured with fMRI and electrophysiology (Krejcar & Namazi, 2025). These models are not final answers, but they are increasingly falsifiable because they can be checked against multiple data types.

What Neuroscience Still Cannot Do

None of this implies that neuroscience has "solved" the mind, consciousness, or the reliable prediction of real-world performance. Major gaps remain. There are practical limitations on how many neurons can be recorded simultaneously in any one experiment. Whole-brain connectomes remain incomplete even for the mouse, let alone the human brain. Linking cellular mechanisms to higher-order cognition and complex clinical phenomena, the questions that matter most for education and mental health are still profoundly difficult (Baghdadi et al., 2025; Krejcar & Namazi, 2025; Nature Methods, 2025). It is also critical to note that nearly all of the cellular-level and connectomic data described above come from animal models, predominantly mice. Human neuroscience still relies principally on non-invasive macro-level imaging methods such as fMRI, MEG, and EEG, which cannot resolve individual neurons or synapses. The species gap between what can be measured in a mouse brain and what can be inferred about a human brain remains a genuine constraint on translating this evidence into educational or clinical practice. Moreover, practical learning and performance in educational settings are also shaped by motivation, relationships, context, fatigue, stress, and culture in ways that do not neatly reduce to neural measures.

Why This Matters Across Educational Settings

The practical takeaway is not that educators should chase brain scans. It is that educational claims that appeal to the brain should be held to a higher standard than "it sounds plausible". We are now in an era where many mechanisms can be directly measured, many explanations can be causally tested (especially in animal models), and some findings can be meaningfully linked to human learning and performance through careful, multi-method evidence.

This applies across diverse educational contexts, including schools, universities, workplaces, aviation and transport training, emergency services, defence, sport, and health and wellbeing education. The goal is better judgment: stronger confidence in well-supported

principles and sharper scepticism of overconfident "neuro" stories. It is no longer accurate to describe cellular-level neuroscience as largely speculative. The field can directly measure, manipulate, and model micro-scale processes and relate them to behaviour and system-level dynamics using converging, empirically grounded methods (Jun et al., 2017; MICrONS Consortium, 2025; Moore et al., 2025; Nature Methods, 2025; Nguyen et al., 2025; Steinmetz et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2025; Yao et al., 2023).

Accuracy matters here because it shapes how we interpret human behaviour and how confidently we speak about the limits of knowledge.

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